

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 11

JANUARY-MARCH ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binás Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DEXTER O. BUTEL

Instructor I

Apayao State College

dexytel022897@gmail.com

“ANG DAHON NG BUKAS”

Sa silong ng punong payak ang buhay niya ay umusbong,
Isang anak ng lupa, sa gutom ay nakikihalong;
Walang diyamante, ginto, o yaman, tanging dahon ang akap
Ngunit sa isip na malikot, may sikreto na kumikislap.

Sa bawat hibla ng dahon, may istoryang hindi pa nagagawa,
Hindi lang pagkain kundi pangarap na sumisibol pa;
Habang mga tao’y dumaraan, siya ay napatitig ng malalim,
At nakita ang bukas sa isang bagay na payak at tahimik.

Sa pagkamalikhain, ang dahon ay naging sa karaniwan,
Hindi lang panlaman tiyan, kundi ideyang may laman;
Ginawa niyang kakaiba ang likas na biyaya,
Isang simpleng obra na sa mundo ay mapagpahanga.

Sa katalinuhan, kanyang sinukat ang lasa at anyo,
Pinanday ang proseso, pinag-aralan ng todo;
Hindi lamang damdamin ang gumabay sa landas,
Kundi talinong matalim, na sa tagumpay ay landas.

Sa imahinasyon, ang gubat ay naging pamilihan,
Ang dahon ay naging yaman na lampas sa isipan;
Nakakita siya ng daigdig na wala pa sa mata,
Isang pangarap na hinabi mula sa hiwaga.

Sa inobasyon, ang dati na payak ay naging pambihira,
Binago ang porma, ginawang bago ang tila luma;
Mula sa dahon na niluto sa apoy ng kahirapan,
Naging produkto itong hinahanap ng sambayanan.

Unti-unting ang pangalan niya ay umalingawngaw,
Mula sa gubat na tahimik hanggang sa bayan na
Mula sa katahimikan sa gubat hanggang sa bayan na maingay;
Ang kahapon na salat ay napalitan ng liwanag,
Dahil sa isip na matapang at pusong hindi kumukupas.

Ngunit hindi niya kinalimotan ang pinanggalingan,
Ang bawat dahon ay paalala ng kanyang pinagpaguran,
Na ang yaman ay hindi lang nasa diyamante at gintong kinang,
Kundi sa isip na lumilikha at pusong may dangal.

Kaya't sa bawat negosyong nais sumibol at tumindig,
Alalahanin ang kwento ng dahong walang imik;
Na ang tagumpay ay bunga ng isip at malikhain,
Matalino, mapangarapin, at buhay'y handang ihain.

For those from SUCs who wish to use this for promotion, the guidelines are stated in the last part.

"Please submit each title as a separate file and rename each file using the title of your work followed by the category of the literary piece.
Example: NAME OF TITLE_POETRY"

Categories

Please **HIGHLIGHT** the category that best fits your submission:

- ◇ **Poetry**
- ◇ Short Stories
- ◇ Essays
- ◇ Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- ◇ Creative Corner
- ◇ Others: _____ (Please specify)

After you fill this out, kindly send it to our official email at **binasbookers2013@gmail.com**. Make sure that your work is final before you send it, as any revisions will no longer be accommodated once the process starts. The entire publication will be posted on our official site once it is finalized, at this link: <https://sites.google.com/view/binasbookers2013/home>

The online publication process typically takes **7 to 10 days**. However, if you opt for a publication that includes **peer review**, the timeline may vary depending on the availability of reviewers. We appreciate your patience and understanding in this matter.

If you want a hand-signed certificate, we can provide you with a copy. However, you will be responsible for the shipping fee: **₱450 for Luzon, ₱300 for Visayas, and ₱450 for Mindanao**.

"This literary magazine will be published both online and in print. The online version is free. After the publication is finalized, we will provide you with the full copy in PDF format. If you wish to print it, you may do so on your own."

FOR SUCs: These are the Guidelines for JC Reclassification

Section 25. Creative Works Produced, Performed, Presented, Exhibited, or Published

1. Creative works encompass a wide range of artistic and intellectual expressions, including, but not limited to, music, dance, drama, theatrical productions, visual arts, architecture, industrial design, and literary publications.

2. Creative works should align with the faculty member's field of specialization. However, creative works outside the faculty member's specialization may be considered, provided that the creative work is supported by and has brought recognition to the SUC, as evidenced by the following:

- a. The faculty member's involvement in creative activities was authorized by the SUC (e.g., special order, memorandum, or official communication);
- b. There is documented evidence that the development of the creative work was supported by the SUC (e.g., approved project proposal, partnership agreements, or authorization for the use of facilities for the creative work);
- c. The creative work has brought recognition to the institution, as demonstrated by awards or other formal acknowledgments received by the SUC, with the SUC's name explicitly cited in the announcement or the university formally recognized as the institution behind the award or recognition.

According to the guideline, ***“Creative works should align with the faculty member's field of specialization,”*** please ensure that your submission aligns with your field. Otherwise, we will rely on the provision in item **c**, which states that the ***“SUC's name [must be] explicitly cited in the announcement or the university formally recognized as the institution behind the award or recognition.”***

Under your name on the certificate, we will indicate your school's name.

